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Budapest University of Technology
and Economics (BME)

PRECISE MODE II FRACTURE TOUGHNESS CONTROL IN HIGH-PERFORMANCE COMPOSITES BY PERFORATED RELEASE FILM INTERLEAVES

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Stiff, strong, lightweight!

Catastrophic failure

Delamination is a frequent failure mode in static and impact load scenarios

Yu Bai, Till Vallée, Thomas Keller, Delamination of pultruded glass fiber-reinforced polymer composites subjected to axial compression, *Composite Structures*, Volume 91, Issue 1, 2009, Pages 66-73, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2009.04.030>.

Gębura, Andrzej. "Application of Electric Capacity Measurements to Detecting Delamination in Blades of Helicopter's Lifting and Auxiliary Rotors" *Polish Maritime Research*, vol. 24, no. 2, Sciendo, 2017, pp. 105-112. <https://doi.org/10.1515/pomr-2017-0056>

Syed Abdullah, S.I.B. (2021). Low Velocity Impact Testing on Laminated Composites. In: Hameed Sultan, M.T., Shah, A.U.M., Saba, N. (eds) *Impact Studies of Composite Materials*. Composites Science and Technology . Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-1323-4_1

Wronkowicz-Katunin, Angelika, and Krzysztof Dragan. "Evaluation of Impact Damage in Composite Structures Using Ultrasonic Testing" *Fatigue of Aircraft Structures*, vol. 2018, no. 10, Sciendo, 2018, pp. 82-92. <https://doi.org/10.2478/fas-2018-0008>

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Introduction

- Laminated composite materials are prone to delamination, which plays a key role in their design
- Film interleaving with tough materials that bond well to the composite plies is an established approach to improve delamination resistance
- Precisely controlled reduction of the fracture toughness is useful to direct delamination damage accumulation to a chosen interface within a laminate
- Perforation patterns for release film interleaves were designed, and their geometry was analysed optically
- Tensile tests on novel central cut layer coupons were executed to obtain the mode II fracture toughness (G_{IIC}) of the interfaces

Materials

Fibre type	Manufacturer	Diameter	Elastic modulus	Strain to failure	Tensile strength	Density
		[μm]	[GPa]	[%]	[GPa]	[kg/m^3]
Flite Strand S-glass	Owens Corning	9	92	3.6-4.4	3.3-4.1	2450
Prepreg type	Manufacturer	Nominal fibre areal density	Fibre volume fraction	Nominal cured ply thickness	Predicted elastic modulus	Failure strain
		[g/m^2]	[%]	[mm]	[GPa]	[%]
S-glass fibre/913 epoxy (GF/EP)	Hexcel	305	49	0.25	47.1	3.9 ^c
Release film type	Manufacturer	Material	Nominal thickness	Tensile strength (both directions)	Failure strain (machine direction)	Failure strain (cross direction)
			[μm]	[MPa]	[%]	[%]
Vabatec RF7	Vabatec	ETFE	15	>40	>170	>300

Perforation pattern design

Quadratic pattern

Quadratic pattern rotated by 45°

Hexagonal pattern

Definition of interlaminar contact area ratio:

$$ICAR = \frac{A_{PERF}}{A_{TOT}} = \frac{D^2 \pi}{4a^2}$$

Centre offset for quadratic pattern:

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{\frac{D^2 \pi}{4}}{ICAR}} = \sqrt{\frac{D^2 \pi}{4(ICAR)}}$$

Coupon design

Design criteria for delamination:

$$G_{II} = \frac{E \varepsilon^2 h t_{cut}}{4(h - t_{cut})}$$

$$t_{cont} > \frac{\varepsilon_{del} E t_{cut}}{2E(\varepsilon_{b GF/EP} - \varepsilon_{del})}$$

Laminate assembly, interleaf positioning

- Patterns were cut with a Versa Laser VLS2.30 type cutting/engraving CO₂ laser with a 10.6 μm wavelength and 30 W maximum power
- Perforated release films were interleaved between prepreg layers manually
- The central ply blocks of the laminates were cut manually with a rotary blade

Pattern designation	Nominal perforation diameter	Nominal interlaminar contact area ratio
	(D _n) [mm]	(ICAR) [-]
D1.5mmICAR0.2	1.5	0.2
D1.5mmICAR0.3	1.5	0.3
D1.5mmICAR0.4	1.5	0.4
D1.5mmICAR0.5	1.5	0.5
D1.0mmICAR0.2	1	0.2
D1.0mmICAR0.3	1	0.3

Perforation pattern geometry assessment

With a **Keyence IM-7020** type image dimension measurement system featuring a 1-inch, 6.6-megapixel monochrome CMOS sensor

Results of optical pattern geometry assessment

Results of optical pattern geometry assessment

Results of optical pattern geometry assessment

	Nominal diameter (D _n)	Measured average diameter (D)	Absolute/relative difference in diameter	Nominal ICAR	Average ICAR calculated from measured data	Difference in ICAR	Total perforation length to cover 100 mm ²
	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]/[%]	[-]	[-]	[-]	[mm]
D1.5mmICAR0.2	1.5	1.617 (0.62)	0.117 / 7.819	0.2	0.233	0.033	53.3
D1.5mmICAR0.3	1.5	1.607 (0.69)	0.107 / 7.140	0.3	0.344	0.044	80.0
D1.5mmICAR0.4	1.5	1.607 (0.72)	0.107 / 7.159	0.4	0.456	0.056	106.7
D1.5mmICAR0.5	1.5	1.581 (0.79)	0.081 / 5.405	0.5	0.557	0.057	133.3
D1mmICAR0.2	1	1.113 (0.97)	0.113 / 11.25	0.2	0.248	0.048	80.0
D1mmICAR0.3	1	1.114 (0.67)	0.114 / 11.38	0.3	0.373	0.073	120.0

Results of G_{IIC} measurements

Results of G_{IIC} measurements

Results of G_{IIC} measurements

	Measured width (W)	Total measured thickness (h)	Estimated cut layer thickness (t_{cut})	Elastic modulus (E)	Delamination stress	Delamination strain	G_{IIC} from stress	Relative difference in G_{IIC}^*
	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[GPa]	[MPa]	[%]	[N/mm]	[%]
Baseline	15.02 (0.14)	1.51 (0.70)	0.503	43.53 (1.34)	673.3 (3.00)	1.564 (4.04)	1.968 (7.24)	5.37
Flattened baseline	15.03 (0.07)	1.47 (1.67)	0.491	43.74 (1.53)	665.9 (1.72)	1.542 (1.42)	1.868 (2.96)	-
D1.6mmICAR0.34	15.04 (0.08)	1.49 (3.40)	0.497	42.54 (1.55)	522.2 (1.94)	1.237 (2.81)	1.194 (3.39)	-36.08
D1.6mmICAR0.46	15.04 (0.08)	1.54 (0.81)	0.512	42.98 (0.93)	605.0 (1.16)	1.424 (1.38)	1.634 (1.74)	-12.52
D1.6mmICAR0.56	15.04 (0.05)	1.52 (0.95)	0.507	43.38 (0.93)	684.9 (1.90)	1.598 (1.66)	2.056 (3.60)	10.07
D1.1mmICAR0.25	15.06 (0.11)	1.52 (1.40)	0.506	42.49 (1.15)	456.8 (2.67)	1.087 (3.57)	0.932 (4.73)	-50.11
D1.1mmICAR0.37	15.07 (0.10)	1.52 (1.14)	0.507	42.30 (1.70)	549.8 (1.57)	1.315 (0.81)	1.359 (1.61)	-27.26

*Compared to the average G_{IIC} of the flattened baseline series.

Conclusions

- Perforation patterns were systematically designed for geometrical characterisation and interface modification.
- **Six** laser-cut perforation **patterns** were **analysed** optically, the **actual perforation diameters were larger** than the nominal values regardless of the nominal diameter.
- The laser-cutting-induced increase in the perforation diameters resulted in a **difference between the nominal and actual interlaminar contact area ratios (ICAR)**. The differences in the ICAR values showed a monotonic increase with the total perforation length.
- Unidirectional composite tensile test coupons having one-third of their plies cut in the central layer were suitable for G_{IIC} assessment.
- The G_{IIC} of the modified laminates **showed a strong linear trend with increasing ICAR**, which enables the control of composite layer interface properties.
- The **maximum reduction of G_{IIC} was up to 50%** with the applied perforation patterns, but the test campaign results indicate that the full range may be covered.
- Baseline laminates with flattened interfaces showed slightly lower G_{IIC} values than the pristine ones.
- The **perforation pattern with the highest ICAR (0.56) increased the G_{IIC} of the laminate by 10%**.
This offers scope for limited, but well-controlled increase of G_{IIC} .

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Thank you for your attention!

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